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Minutes of the 110th meeting of the EFSA Working Group on pest survey cards: Review of the pest survey card on *Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus* and *P. pruinus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Meeting held 20 September 2022; minutes approved by participants 30 September 2022.

Participants: Ignazio Graziosi (EFSA, chair), Cecile Robin (French National Institute for Agriculture Food and Environment, working group expert), Robert Rabaglia (Forest Service US Department of Agriculture, hearing expert).

In accordance with EFSA's Policy on Independence¹ and the Decision of the Executive Director on Competing Interest Management², EFSA screened the Annual Declarations of Interest filled out by the Working Group members invited to the present meeting. No Conflicts of Interest related to the issues discussed in this meeting have been identified during the screening process, and no interests were declared orally by the members at the beginning of this meeting.

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Review of the survey card on *Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus* and *P. pruinus*

The Working Group reviewed the draft of the survey card on *Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus* and *P. pruinus* (EFSA-Q-2022-00143). The pest survey card is prepared in the context of the EFSA mandate on plant pest surveillance (M-2020-0114) at the request of the European Commission, with the purpose of assisting EU Member States in preparing data and information for surveys of quarantine pests. *Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus* and *P. pruinus* are Union quarantine pests (QP) with North and Central American distribution, not known to occur in the EU.

Hearing expert Robert Rabaglia provided detailed answers to specific questions. WG member Cecile Robin added specific input, formulated specific questions and provided overall feedback on the conclusions of the document.

Questions and Answers (RR: Robert Rabaglia, CR: Cecile Robin)

1. When there are more than one generation per year, do we know the timing of the developmental stages for each generation?

RR: Wide range for both species. In Wisconsin there is 1 generation per year. In Missouri and Texas multiple gen. per year. N of generation is function of the climate more of the species. In Texas: continuous, generations all year long. In Wisconsin discrete generations, 1 to 1.5, with adults emerging in July.

2. After overwintering, the adults reach healthy trees where they perform maturation feeding and they then search for unhealthy trees for reproduction. They emerge from these unhealthy trees as adults

¹ http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/corporate_publications/files/policy_independence.pdf

² http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/corporate_publications/files/competing_interest_management_17.pdf

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that will produce the second generation. If the unhealthy tree is already infected by *Bretziella fagacearum*, the adults of the second generation emerging from the unhealthy tree can transmit the disease to a healthy tree where they will do maturation feeding. Is this true?

CR: Possible but less frequent. Transmission by second gen is possible but less frequent than first generation. See Gibbs and French 1980.

Gibbs JN and French DW, 1980. The transmission of oak wilt. Research Paper NC-185, North Central Forest Experiment Station, USDA Forest Service, St. Paul, USA, 22 pp. Available online: <https://www.fs.usda.gov/treearch/pubs/10706>

RR: Infection rate of both is very low, around 1% in Missouri. They are attracted by unhealthy trees, dying trees, small branches, not necessary by trees infected by oak wilt. Not sure which generation has higher infection rate, possibly the second. They are more important for white oak rather than red oak in term of transmission rate. See Ambourn et al. 2006 and Juzwik 2007.

Ambourn AK, Juzwik J, Eggers JE, 2006. Flight periodicities, phoresy rates, and levels of *Pseudopityophthorus minutissimus* branch colonization in oak wilt centers. Forest Science, 52(3): 243-250.

Juzwik J, 2007. Epidemiology and occurrence of oak wilt in Midwestern, Middle, and South Atlantic states. In: Proceedings of the national oak wilt symposium 4 Jun 2007 (pp. 4-7).

3. If there is no second generation, overwintering adults which emerged from the trees infected by *B. fagacearum* can have the spores during the overwintering and they can transmit them to a new healthy host during maturation feeding next year after overwintering. Is this true?

RR and **CR:** yes.

4. The relevant literature is not clear about the symptoms of the oak bark beetles. Symptoms are linked to (and match with) *B. fagacearum* wilt symptoms. Can the two bark beetle species cause wilt without any *B. fagacearum* infection?

CR: By themselves the bark beetles do not induce tree wilt.

RR: if the beetles do not vector the fungus, they will not cause any wilt by themselves on healthy trees.

5. If we imagine beetle population is quite high, will the symptoms of maturation feeding on leaves be noticeable? Or other symptoms?

RR: Not necessary. It varies greatly. In the Washington DC area there are a lot of white oak dying (root flooding followed by drought) with no oak wilt, but a lot of *Pseudopityophthorus* contributing to the decline.

6. Is there any knowledge on the efficacy and attraction range of traps?

RR: pheromone is not known. They do respond to ethanol (anecdotal data suggest). Range is not very far: few meters (10 m or less), like for the walnut twig beetle.

If there is a good host in the vicinity they don't go very far, and it depends also on how healthy are the beetles. For comparison, the attraction range of the pheromone for *Pityophthorus juglandis* is not very far. 50-100 meters at most. This is based on some unpublished data from Steve Seybold and colleagues in California. See literature on the walnut twig beetle *Pityophthorus juglandis* (vector of thousand cankers disease) by SJ Seybold.

7. Is there any knowledge on the dispersal capacity of the adult beetles? For a similar sized beetle (*Pityogenus calcographus*) dispersal is around 86 km but can we use that? Faccoli evaluated 9.5km for *P. juglandis*.

RR: Dispersal is not known. Dispersal of the two *Pseudopityophthorus* can be assumed to be similar to the one of *P. juglandis*. See papers on the walnut twig beetle *P. juglandis* by SJ Seybold.

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I do not have any hard data but it also is not very far. Most beetles will stay on the same tree as long as it is still of good quality for breeding. Some studies on *Orthotomicus* by SJ Seybold evaluate the dispersal in 2km.

8. (CR) Is there any observation of the two *Pseudopityophthorus* on *Castanea dentata* and European oaks (sentinel trees in USA?)

RR: Not that I know. They supposedly have very large host range. Sentinel project with Euro oaks in NH and OH. *Castanea floridana* (*Castanea pumila*) there is a record. Records of non-oak hosts for breeding or maturation feeding of *P. minutissimus* and *pruinusus* are largely unknown. I know of some observations from Atkinson regarding breeding in *Prunus* in Mexico for other *Pseudopityophthorus* spp., but it is unclear if host records other than oaks are for maturation feeding or breeding.

9. How much are the galleries distinctive?

RR. The galleries of *Pseudopityophthorus* are very distinctive and no like even *Pityophthorus*, so that may be helpful when looking at potentially infested wood.
